

STRUCTURE AND FRACTURE - TOUGHNESS OF AN
ORIENTED EUTECTIC ALLOY, Co/Ni-Cr₂₃C₆

G. Zambelli - W. Kurz

Materials Department

Swiss Federal Institute of Technology

Lausanne / Switzerland

The oriented pseudo-binary eutectic alloy Co/Ni-Cr₂₃C₆ possesses excellent mechanical properties at high temperatures together with good corrosion resistance. However, brittleness at ambient temperatures diminishes its possible applications. An improvement in fracture toughness can be obtained by modifying three factors: fracture strength, plastic deformation of the phases and crack interface interactions.

These factors depend mainly on the structural parameters of the alloy, for example, the dimensions, shape, distribution and volume fraction of the phases. The aim of the present work is to verify the influence of these parameters on the fracture behaviour, taking as a measure of toughness the total fracture work γ_f (three-point bending tests).

The results obtained show that within the limits of the study, the variation in intercarbide spacing and the thickness of the carbides have no effect on the toughness: the fracture remaining unstable and brittle. This result may be due to the continuous nature of the carbides. A modification of the Co/Ni ratio results in a variation both of the volume fraction of the complex carbides and of the composition of the two phases.

Increasing the Ni content of the ductile phase ($Ni/Ni+Co \geq 0.3$) causes a slight but progressive improvement in toughness. This increase can be related to the effect of the change of crystal structure (cph Co to fcc Ni) of the ductile phase. The propagation of the crack remains unstable, except for alloys with high nickel con-

tents (Ni/Ni+Co \geq 0.8).

A model is proposed for the fracture mechanism in this type of alloy. The crack seems to choose an optimum path through the structure, maximising propagation in the continuous brittle $M_{23}C_6$ carbides and minimising propagation in the ductile phase (Co,Ni). The crack will choose the path closest to that involving minimum fracture energy. In order to increase the toughness of these alloys, this minimum has to be increased.

1. INTRODUCTION

The object of this study is an analysis of the fracture behaviour of oriented, pseudo-binary, eutectic alloys of the type (Co,Ni)-Cr₂₃C₆. These alloys give a composite structure consisting of a ductile phase (Co,Ni) reinforced by a large volume fraction ($\approx 40\%$) of brittle (Cr,Co,Ni)₂₃C₆ carbides. Their high temperature properties are promising (Thompson and Lemkey, 1974), but their brittleness at room temperature limits their usefulness. It is therefore important to improve their toughness.

The total work γ_F absorbed during crack propagation gives a measure of toughness which can be related to various energy dissipating mechanisms occurring during crack growth. γ_F is only measurable in the case of stable crack propagation.

Figure 1 gives the load-deflection curves for unstable crack propagation (a), and semi-controlled propagation (b). Stable crack propagation (c) conditions are fulfilled in the case of three-point bending of a triangular-notch test-piece as shown in figure 1 (Tattersall and Tappin, 1966). The high stress concentration at the apex of the triangular bridge favours crack initiation under small loads. The fracture work, γ_F , measured corresponds to the area under the load/deflection curve (c in figure 1).

An improvement in fracture toughness, γ_F , can be obtained by modifying three factors (figure 2):

- A) Fracture strength (elastic limit)
- B) Plastic deformation of one or more phases
- C) Crack/interface interactions

Generally, for eutectic composites with brittle fibres, the increase in fracture strength (A in figure 2) will be a function of the size, shape, and distribution of the reinforcing phase. The interphase spacing λ can affect the pile-up stress at the interfaces, creating a reinforcement of the ductile phase and influencing crack initiation. Account must also be taken of residual stresses induced by the difference in thermal dilatation of the two phases (Koss and Kopley, 1971) and of imperfections in the brittle fibre, which will decrease the maximum strength of the eutectic alloy (Thompson, Koss, and Chesnutt, 1970).

The ductilisation (B in figure 2) of an eutectic composite with a ductile matrix will depend on the ability of the matrix to work-harden and to deform between the broken fibres. A high ductility may be observed due to the presence of active slip planes parallel to the fibres (Thompson, 1971). This will be a function of the angle between the applied stress and the orienta-

tion of the fibres. For a brittle matrix eutectic, the deformation energy of the ductile fibres can improve the fracture energy of the composite. This leads to an increase in the critical defect length or to stable crack growth (Antolovich, 1970).

In composites with weak interfacial bonding, the fracture toughness is increased by energy absorbing mechanisms such as fibre pullout, decohesion, and crack deviation (Cooper, 1971). These effects also contribute to crack stabilisation (C in figure 2). However, the creation of the necessary weak interfacial bonding is difficult to obtain in eutectic composites and, moreover, appears undesirable because the high temperature stability may be impaired.

Finally, a maximum in fracture energy may be obtained by the combined action of the proposed mechanisms (D in figure 2). For the (Co,Ni)-Cr₂₃C₆ eutectic, with carbides distributed in a ductile phase, the principle methods for changing the toughness are to vary the size and distribution of the carbides (factor A) and the amount of deformation work of the ductile phase (factor B). This study investigates these effects.

2. EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

The Co-Ni-Cr-C-system contains, under a saddlepoint, a two-phase region (Co,Ni-M₂₃C₆, M = Cr,Co,Ni) which offers the interesting possibility of varying the volume fraction, and the composition of the phases (Thompson and Lemkey, 1974).

The preparation of the alloys (table I) is carried out by melting the high-purity elements (Co and Ni 99.9%; Cr 99.99%) under argon in alumina crucibles. Each charge is sucked into quartz tubes. The cast rods are then melted in alumina tubes and directionally solidified in a furnace with a temperature gradient of about 90°C/cm.

Observation of the microstructures is carried out on polished sections etched with a 20% solution of potassium ferricyanide in water at 70°C.

The slow three point bend tests for the measurement of fracture work, γ_F , were performed on an Instron tensile testing machine. The test-piece is a 4 mm square bar, 30 mm in length with a triangular notch made with a 0.3 mm diamond wheel (figure 1), and the test speed is 0.05 cm/min.

Complementary tests have been carried out on single-edge-notch-

ed beam (SENB) specimens to determine the energy, γ , required for the crack propagation in the notch. In our tests, a fine notch of finite dimensions (width 0.3 mm, $\rho \sim 0.15$ mm, made using a diamond wheel) was used to represent the initially induced crack.

The use of a machined notch has been justified by Simpson (1974) by comparing the fracture stress of a sharp crack and a machined notch of radius ≈ 0.15 mm in dense ceramics. We assume that a similar situation exists at the root of the machined notch in our composites.

3. EVALUATION OF THE MICROSTRUCTURAL PARAMETERS

Figure 3 shows a typical microphotograph of the directionally solidified eutectic alloy (Co,Ni)- $M_{23}C_6$, with the ductile phase composition Ni/Ni+Co = 0.3 (alloy D in table I). Figure 4 is a scanning electron microphoto (S.E.M.) of the microstructure after partial dissolution of the matrix. This microstructure reveals the characteristic morphology of the $M_{23}C_6$ type carbides which form a 'skeleton' having no preferred orientation. The interconnection of the $M_{23}C_6$ carbides (figure 4) permits one to consider the alloy as a composite containing continuous ductile and brittle phases (symbols (d) and (c) respectively).

The structure of an alloy with a dispersed phase, can be described in terms of the volume fraction (V) and the average diameter or thickness (t) of the particles.

The interphase spacing λ will be a function of these two parameters. The mean free distance in the ductile phase λ can be described in terms of the average distance between the interfaces of the particles measured along a straight line drawn at random on a transverse cut (Fullmann, 1953):

$$\lambda_D = \frac{1-V}{N_L} = t \left[\frac{1}{V} - 1 \right] \quad (1)$$

$$\lambda = \lambda_D + t$$

where N_L is the number of particles per unit length, and t the linear measure of the effective size of the particle. These relations are general and can be applied in the absence of any supposition as to the morphology of the particles. Measurement of the parameters λ_D , t and V were carried out with the aid of an image analyser (IMANCO 720). Analysis of the frequency function of particles having undergone a progressive image erosion permits one to define an average 'thickness' λ_C of the carbide, attributable to the quantity t. Figure 5 gives an example of the relative fre-

quency curves for the number of intercepts counted in horizontal scans of transverse sections. These curves represent the number of intercepts measured at various stages in the progressive erosion of the image of the two phases. The maxima of the curves correspond to the most frequent intercept values, λ_C and λ_D : 1.3 μm and 2.5 μm respectively. The asymmetrical distribution around the maxima results from the skeleton form of the carbides. The median values, $\bar{\lambda}_C = 2.3 \mu\text{m}$ and $\bar{\lambda}_D = 3.6 \mu\text{m}$ are displaced to the right of the maximum. This tendency is related to the branching of the carbides. The volume fraction of the carbides and the thickness of the phases, λ_C and λ_D , measured follow the relations of quantitative metallography (equation 1). The intercarbide spacing λ is assumed equal to λ_C plus λ_D .

The variation of the intercarbide spacing λ for the alloy (D) depends on the solidification speed, R , according to the relation (figure 6):

$$\lambda^{3.6} R = \text{constant.}$$

The exponent of 3.6 is very high for an eutectic. One normally finds a value of 2 - even for systems where one phase grows with a large kinetic undercooling e.g. Fe-C (Frederickson, 1975). It is interesting to note that the (Co,Cr)-(Cr,Co)₇C₃ -system seems to give an exponent of 3.8 (figure 6; Fritscher, Wirth and Bunk, 1973).

The structure of the alloys studied becomes cellular, with the formation of M₇C₃ carbides, at $R \geq 1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$ cm/sec.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Microstructures

Spacing

For the oriented eutectic alloy Co,Ni-M₂₃C₆ (D in table I) at solidification speeds $R > 1.7 \cdot 10^{-5}$ cm/sec, variation of λ_D ($2.2 \mu\text{m} < \lambda_D < 4.6 \mu\text{m}$) has no significant effect on the measured fracture work, γ_F . There is a small improvement in its value ($2 \times 10^3 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$, figure 7) with increasing λ_D . For the structure obtained at a very low speed, $R = 1.7 \times 10^{-5}$ cm/sec ($\lambda_D = 9.6 \mu\text{m}$), γ_F increases to 3.10^3 Jm^{-2} . A progressive decrease in volume fraction of carbides, V_C , from 0.50 to 0.28, is observed with increasing λ_D and λ_F . This can be attributed to the effects of decarburisation of the molten zone by reaction between the alloy and the alumina crucible.

Orientation

A cast structure with equiaxed grains was also prepared from

alloy D. The average value of fracture work, γ_F , measured was $3.2 \times 10^3 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$. This value is similar to that obtained for structures oriented at low speed. Therefore, the orientation of eutectic grains has no observable influence on the fracture process. This is reasonable since the morphology of the $M_{23}C_6$ carbides is non-oriented.

4.2 Influence of the matrix composition

Multivariant eutectic alloys comprising a Co-matrix and chromium carbides permit the substitution of other elements (Ni, Fe, Mn, etc.) without modifying the overall morphology of the alloy. The case of Ni is especially interesting as it stabilises the fcc matrix and lowers the volume fraction of carbides ($V_C \approx 0.5$ for Co and ≈ 0.3 for Ni).

The alloys studied, ranging from ones with Co-Cr to those with Ni-Cr matrix (table I), were all prepared under the same conditions with solidification speed, R , equal to $6.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm/sec}$.

The transition in crystal structure from oph Co-matrix to fcc Ni-matrix occurs for an alloy of some 15% Ni (room temperature and corresponding to a Ni/Ni+Co ratio in the ductile phase of about 0.3), i.e. alloy D discussed in 4.1. This transition (figure 8) is accompanied by a rapid decrease in hardness of the ductile phase, related to the increase in stacking fault energy due to the stabilisation of the fcc structure by Ni. The amount of carbide formed remains constant ($V_C \approx 0.50$) for those alloys containing up to 40 wt. % Ni (Ni/Ni+Co = 0.8) and having a constant Cr/C ratio. The alloy Ni- $M_{23}C_6$ (K), with a higher Cr/C ratio, exhibits a decrease in volume fraction of carbides ($V_C \approx 0.32$).

In spite of the type of test adopted, an unstable fracture mode was recorded for most of these alloys (figure 9). The fracture work, γ_F^U , measured for unstable crack propagation does not correspond to the total work of crack propagation γ_F . This unstable mode indicates that the energy necessary to initiate the crack at the apex of the triangular fracture surface is higher than the energy for crack propagation. The values measured for unstable cracking γ_F^U were assumed to be equal to the total energy of crack propagation γ_F . Even with the wide scatter, there is a distinct tendency for the fracture work, γ_F , to increase with Ni content (figure 10). The average value of the fracture work, γ_F ; $3 \times 10^3 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$ for Co,Ni- $M_{23}C_6$ (low Ni content), increases to $4.75 \times 10^3 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$ for the alloy Ni- $M_{23}C_6$ (K). This increase in toughness is accompanied by fracture stabilisation (figure 9), particularly for alloys having a Ni content greater than 35 wt.% (Ni/Ni+Co > 0.7). In this case, the ductile fcc Ni,Co phase seems to play

a not unimportant rôle in the fracture behaviour of the eutectic composite.

4.3 Fracture surface

Fracture is probably initiated either by microcracks in the carbides, due to their already existing geometric or structural defects, or by an accumulation of dislocations from the ductile phase leading to stress concentration at the matrix/carbide interface.

Micrographic examination of sections perpendicular to the fracture surface shows a preferred propagation of the crack through the carbides, with occasional deviation (figure 11). A S.E.M. microfractographic study (figure 12a) shows that there exist dimpled zones of ductile fracture, in the (Co,Ni) phase, at the edges of the smooth, brittle fracture carbide surfaces. However, a large extent of smooth surfaces (fractured carbides) with steps is observed on the fracture surface. The crack propagates mainly through the carbides, which constitute a continuous brittle phase. A similar fracture mechanism is observed in the ternary eutectic alloy Al-Cu-Mg (Garmong and Rhodes, 1972). In this case, the crack propagates through the two brittle phases (CuMgAl₂ lamellae and CuAl₂ rods), completely by-passing the ductile Al phase.

Various tests were made to determine the volume fraction of the ductile phase participating in the rupture process (V_D^R). Figure 12 compares the same area on the fracture surface before and after preferential etching to remove the ductile phase. For alloy D ($R = 1.7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm/sec}^{-1}$) which has a low volume fraction of large carbides ($V_C \approx 0.22$), the volume of the ductile phase taking part in the final fracture is $V_D^R \approx 0.1$. Therefore, the volume of ductile phase involved in fracture is about four times smaller than that measured on a transverse cut.

5. DISCUSSION

Within the limits of this study, the variation of the inter-carbide spacing λ_D and thickness, λ_C , has no direct influence on the toughness of the brittle eutectic alloys Co,Ni-M₂₃C₆. No effect of the variation of the size of the phases on the fracture work γ_F (Hall-Petch type relation) is therefore proved for this alloy (A, figure 2). The results show an increase in fracture work, γ_F , which depends mainly on I) the capacity of the ductile phase to absorb the stresses at the tips of the cracks formed in the carbides and II) the contribution to fracture of the deformation work of this phase (B, figure 2).

The equivalence of total fracture work, γ_F , and critical stress intensity factor K_{IC} can be assumed only in the case of stable crack propagation.

A three point bend test using a single-edge-notched beam (SENB) (notch depth = c) is a classic method of measuring the stress intensity factor K_I (Brown and Strawley, 1967):

$$K_I = Y\sigma(c)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

where σ is the fracture stress and Y is a geometric factor. The relation (2) holds for a state of plane stress. This measure of K_I is only valid for a mathematically sharp crack.

The factor K_I was measured for alloy (D) solidified (6.7×10^{-4} cm/sec) using an SENB-specimen. The measurements verified the fact that K_I is independent of variation in notch depth, c. The principles of linear fracture mechanics are therefore applicable and the equivalence of K_I and K_{IC} could be assumed. The average measured value of K_{IC} was $10.8 \text{ MNm}^{-3/2}$.

The critical energy of crack propagation G_{IC} in an ideally brittle material is given by the Griffith criterion:

$$G_{IC} = 2\gamma_s \quad (3)$$

where γ_s is the surface energy.

If one considers a two-phase system, the total energy G_{IC} dissipated per unit surface of crack propagation can be approximately defined as the sum of the individual energies for the phases weighted by their volume fraction:

$$G_{IC} = G_{IC}^d V_d + G_{IC}^c (1-V_d) \quad (4)$$

where G_{IC}^d = energy for the ductile phase and G_{IC}^c = energy for the carbides.

The theory of linear fracture mechanics gives a relationship between G_{IC} and the critical stress intensity factor K_{IC} for the case of plane strain:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{K_{IC}^2}{E} (1-\nu^2) \quad (5)$$

where: ν = Poisson's constant and E = Young's modulus.

By choosing an empirical value for G_{IC} of $\approx 40 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$, which seems to be of the correct order of magnitude for the carbides

(Pabst, 1974), an approximate value of G_{IC}^d can be measured by supposing that (4) and (5) are applicable to the brittle eutectic composite studied.

The calculation of G_{IC} for the composite is carried out starting from the measured value of K_{IC} and assuming for the other quantities:

$$\begin{aligned} E &= 276 \text{ GNM}^{-2} \text{ (Thompson, Lemkey, 1974)} \\ \nu &= 0.3 \\ V_D^R &= 0.1 \text{ (see chapter 4.1.)} \end{aligned}$$

The following values were calculated:

$$\begin{aligned} G_{IC} \text{ (composite)} &\approx 1.44 \times 10^3 \text{ Jm}^{-2} \\ G_{IC} \text{ (ductile phase)} &\approx 14 \times 10^3 \text{ Jm}^{-2} \end{aligned}$$

According to (3) (but for a total energy Y), one finds an energy for unstable crack propagation, Y , of $0.72 \times 10^3 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$ for the eutectic alloy D. The measured average value of the total fracture work for the unstable crack propagation, $Y_F^U = 2 \times 10^3 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$, i.e. $Y_F^U \approx 3Y$.

In the case of alloy D solidified at $1.7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm/sec}$. ($\lambda_C \approx 9.6\mu$), the contribution of the ductile phase to the fracture process is greater ($V_D \approx 0.2$, chapter 4.1.). The calculated value of Y was $1.43 \times 10^3 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$, while the measured value of Y_F was $\approx 3 \times 10^3$ (figure 9). These results show that $Y_F = 2Y$.

The larger values of Y_F^U in comparison with Y can be attributed to the potential energy released on failure exceeding the energy necessary for overall instability. This excess of energy depends on the difference in initiation effects at the apex of the triangular fracture section and the tip of the notch in SENB specimens. The diminution of this excess energy with increase in V_D^R is attributed to energy dissipating processes such as plastic flow at the crack tip.

As already shown, the fracture of the alloys is characterised by preferential propagation of the crack through the continuous $M_{23}C_6$ -carbides, avoiding most of the ductile phase. Figure 13 shows that there may exist an optimum condition: crack propagation along the path of lowest fracture energy. The specific fracture energy as a function of the effective volume fraction of the ductile phase ($V_D = 1 - V_C$) will follow the rule of mixtures (figure 13b) when there is no interaction between the phases, e.g. low strength of the ductile phase. The creation of a higher effective volume of the brittle or the ductile phase at the fracture

surface will necessitate the creation of a rough surface (this being a function of the morphology of the phase) and therefore, the effective fracture surface will increase (figure 13a). The summation of these effects will give the curve in figure 13b, assuming that there exists a minimum in the total fracture energy σ_{IC}^{min} determining the effective volume fraction of the phases at the fracture surface. Following this argument, the morphology of the carbides should be an important factor in the toughness of these composites.

A slight but progressive increase in total fracture work was observed for increasing Ni content (figure 10). When the volume fraction of the ductile phase increases, for alloys with Ni/Ni+Co ≥ 0.8 (figure 8), stabilisation of crack propagation is found. The results obtained show clearly that the ductile phase seems to play a determining rôle in increasing the toughness of the alloy.

Tests carried out on the alloy Co-M₇C₃ [L] ($V_D = 0.3$) indicated a fracture work of $\gamma_F = 7.5 \times 10^3 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$, i.e. a value three times greater than that measured for the alloy Co-M₂₃C₆ [A]. In Co-M₇C₃, the carbides solidify in the form of irregular polygonal fibres, generally isolated from one another, in a Co-matrix. In this case, the microstructure consists of a non-continuous brittle phase. Therefore the propagation of the crack can be stopped by the ductile phase (matrix) before it becomes supercritical. The importance of structures having a very high volume fraction of the brittle phase has been shown in a previous study (Zambelli and Kurz, 1972).

6. CONCLUSIONS

A study of the influence of structural parameters on the fracture work γ_F was carried out in order to determine conditions for increasing the toughness of the brittle eutectic alloys (Co,Ni)-M₂₃C₆.

Within the ranges considered ($\lambda_D = 2.5$ to $10 \mu\text{m}$ and $\lambda_C = 2.5$ to $5 \mu\text{m}$) the variation of the intercarbide spacing λ_D and carbide thickness λ_C has no influence on the toughness ($\gamma_F \approx 2 \times 10^3 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$). The fracture remains unstable and brittle. The brittle character of the fracture can be attributed to the spatial continuity of the brittle phase (M₂₃C₆ carbides). Decrease in volume fraction of the carbides plays a large part in increasing toughness, due to the influence of the ductile phase during fracture.

Increasing the Ni content of the ductile phase (Ni/Ni+Co ≥ 0.3) causes a slight but progressive improvement in toughness.

This increase can be related to the effect of the change of crystal structure (cph Co to fcc Ni) of the ductile phase. The propagation of the crack remains unstable, except for alloys with high nickel contents ($\text{Ni}/\text{Ni}+\text{Co} \geq 0.8$).

Generally, the fracture of the alloys is characterised by the preferential propagation of the crack through the continuous M_{23}C_6 carbides, which causes an increase in length of the fracture path. The fracture work of the ductile phase (Co, Ni), even for small effective volumes, is not negligible. The crack seems to try to find an optimal path through the structure: by avoiding the ductile phase, the effective volume fraction of the brittle phase increases, thus decreasing the fracture energy. However, this process increases the effective fracture surface area. The crack will choose a path close to a minimum of fracture energy (figure 13). In order to increase the toughness of these alloys, therefore, this minimum has to be increased.

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Table I

Co - Ni - Cr - C Alloys

Alloy	Composition of Matrix Ni Ni+Co (weight fraction)	Composition of alloy (weight percentage)				Microstructure
		Co	Ni	Cr	C	
A	0	49	--	49	2	Co-M ₂₃ C ₆
B	0.1	45	5	48	2	} Ni/Co-M ₂₃ C ₆
C	0.2	40	10	48	2	
D	0.3	34	15	49	2	
E	0.4	30	20	48	2	
F	0.5	25	25	48	2	
G	0.6	20	30	48	2	
H	0.8	10	40	48	2	} Ni/Co-M ₂₃ C ₆
K	1.0	--	46.4	52	1.6	Ni-M ₂₃ C ₆
L	0	56.6	--	41	2.4	Co-M ₇ C ₃

1. Load-deflection curve for:

- unstable crack propagation
- semi-controlled crack propagation
- stable crack propagation

2. Improvement in fracture toughness by:

- Increase in fracture strength (elastic limit)
- Increase in plastic deformation
- Crack stabilisation
- Combined action of the above mechanisms

3. Oriented eutectic alloy Co,Ni- $M_{23}C_6$ (alloy D), transverse section $R = 6.7 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ cm sec}^{-1}$
(gray phase = carbides, white phase = Co,Ni)

4. Morphology of $M_{23}C_6$ carbides (same alloy as in fig. 3), after deep etching of ductile phase

5. Relative distribution of intercept values $\Delta I/\Delta I^{\max}$ in relation to the particle erosion Δ (alloy as in fig. 3, λ_c, λ_d = maximum values; $\bar{\lambda}_c, \bar{\lambda}_d$ = median values)

6. Relation between the interphase spacing λ (maximum of fig. 5) and the solidification rate R for alloy D (black dots)- white dots: $\text{Co-M}_7\text{C}_3$ after Fritscher, Wirth and Bunk, 1973

7. Total fracture work γ_F and volume fraction of carbides V_C as a function of thickness or interphase spacing λ_D for alloy D (● Average of 3, ○ Average of 25 measurements)

8. Microhardness in relation to the Ni-content in the ductile phase (● Average of 10, ○ Average of 25 measurements)

9. Load-deflection curve for alloys $\text{Co-M}_7\text{C}_3$ / $\text{Co-M}_{23}\text{C}_6$ / $\text{Co, Ni 15-M}_{23}\text{C}_6$ and $\text{Ni-M}_{23}\text{C}_6$ in three-point bending

10. Total fracture work γ_f in relation to the Ni-content in the ductile phase (o Average of 3 tests)

11. Microstructure perpendicular to the fracture surface, alloy D,
 $R = 6.7 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ cm sec}^{-1}$

12. Fracture surface (alloy D, $R = 1.67 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ cm sec}^{-1}$)
a) before etching, b) after dissolution of the ductile phase

13. Influence of the ratio: Fracture surface A_R to transverse section A_T on G_{Ic} for the case of an alloy with 50 Vol% carbides in the transverse section ($A_R/A_T = 1$) and 80 Vol% carbides in the fracture surface